

Teachers' Ancillary Services Across School Sizes in The Fourth Congressional District of Quezon Province: Its Impact on the Learners' Academic Performance

Ramil Cuya ¹, Leodegario M. Jalos, Jr. ²

¹ Department of Education, ² Marinduque State University

¹ ramil.cuya@deped.gov.ph, ² leodegario74@gmail.com

Article Details:

Received: 17 February 2026

Revised: 21 February 2026

Accepted: 24 February 2026

Published: 28 February 2026

Corresponding Email:

ramil.cuya@deped.gov.ph

Recommended Citation:

Cuya, R., Jalos L. M. (2026). Teachers' Ancillary Services Across School Sizes in The Fourth Congressional District of Quezon Province: Its Impact on the Learners' Academic Performance. *The International Review of Multidisciplinary Research*, 1 (2), 121-137.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18832068>

Index Terms:

learners' academic performance, teachers' ancillary services, number of hours, number of years

Abstract. This study examined the impact of teachers' ancillary services on learners' academic performance across school sizes within the Fourth Congressional District of Quezon Province. It sought to determine the status of teachers' ancillary services in terms of identified assignments, number of hours rendered, and years of service; the academic performance of learners under teachers with ancillary duties; the significant difference in the impact of ancillary services among schools of different sizes; and the possible policy intervention that may be proposed based on the findings. A descriptive-quantitative research design was employed, with a validated survey questionnaire administered to 537 teachers from 28 public elementary schools. The data were analyzed using frequency and percentage, weighted mean and standard deviation, and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). Findings revealed that all teachers were assigned to at least one ancillary service, with many handling multiple roles, including ICT, SBM, LIS/EBEIS, and Health Coordination. The majority spent 2 to 3 hours daily on ancillary work, and more than half had served in these roles for over 3 years. Results also showed that small schools had the greatest impact from ancillary duties (WM = 3.40), followed by medium schools (WM = 2.76) and large schools (WM = 2.36). The computed ANOVA ($F = 18.35$, $p < 0.05$) indicated a significant difference in the impact levels among school sizes. Learners' average grades were slightly lower in small schools with heavier ancillary workloads. The study concludes that ancillary services significantly affect academic performance, particularly in small schools, and that equitable workload policies are necessary to prioritize instruction.

Introduction

Education plays a vital role in shaping learners' intellectual, social, and emotional development. The success of educational institutions largely depends on the effective performance and commitment of teachers, who are the cornerstone of academic excellence. Their primary responsibility is to deliver quality instruction and facilitate learning that promotes academic success and holistic development. However, teachers' roles extend beyond classroom teaching; they are also expected to contribute to the school's overall functioning through various support roles.

In addition to their instructional duties, teachers are often assigned ancillary responsibilities, such as coordinating school programs, preparing reports, handling administrative work, supervising co-curricular activities, and participating in school committees. These non-teaching responsibilities are essential for maintaining school operations and implementing educational programs effectively. Nevertheless, these tasks may reduce the time and energy teachers can devote to lesson preparation, classroom management, and direct instruction, thereby affecting learners' academic performance.

In the Philippine educational context, particularly in public schools, the Department of Education recognizes the importance of ancillary services in ensuring the smooth implementation of school programs. However, it also acknowledges the

additional burden these duties impose on teachers. The distribution of ancillary services varies by school size—small, medium, and large—leading to differences in teachers' workloads and time management. These variations may influence the quality of instruction and the overall learning environment.

In smaller schools, teachers often take on multiple ancillary roles due to limited staff, resulting in heavier workloads and potential role overload. Medium-sized schools may have more staff, yet teachers may still experience overlapping responsibilities. In large schools, even with more teachers, the complexity and volume of administrative and organizational tasks may still require significant time and attention. These conditions suggest that school size plays a crucial role in determining how ancillary services are assigned and managed.

Learners' academic performance, commonly measured by grades and learning outcomes, is an important indicator of educational quality and teacher effectiveness. When teachers spend substantial time on non-teaching tasks, their focus on instructional planning and delivery may decrease, potentially leading to lower academic achievement among students. On the other hand, when ancillary services are well-organized and equitably distributed, they can enhance school operations, support student engagement, and indirectly contribute to improved academic performance.

Several studies have shown that teachers' workload, job satisfaction, and teaching effectiveness are closely linked to student achievement. Excessive ancillary duties can lead to stress, fatigue, and burnout, which can negatively affect classroom performance. Conversely, balanced workloads and supportive school management can strengthen teacher morale and improve instructional quality. These findings highlight the importance of examining how ancillary services interact with teaching responsibilities, particularly across schools of different sizes.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive survey design because it involved measurement, classification, analysis, comparison, and interpretation. Additionally, this study involved collecting information by interviewing a sample of individuals and administering questionnaires.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in the Fourth Congressional District of Quezon Province. The district comprises municipalities in the Tayabas Isthmus and Alabat Island, including Alabat, Atimonan, Calauag, Guinayangan, Gumaca, Lopez, Perez, Plaridel, Quezon, and Tagkawayan. The study covered 28 schools within small, medium, and large schools. However, only three elementary schools in each municipality were selected.

Research Population and Sample

Three schools in each school district from the Fourth Congressional District of the Division of Quezon were identified. For each district, schools were selected by identifying one large, one medium-sized, and one small school. All teachers at the chosen schools were the respondents of this study.

Research Instrument

The principal instrument used to gather essential information for the study was a questionnaire. The questionnaire was first assessed by the research adviser and then validated by the district supervisor, principal, department, and master teachers to ensure it was appropriate and reliable. The questionnaire is a checklist-style questionnaire in which each respondent answered all items to the best of their knowledge, based on the current situation.

Data Gathering Procedures

Prior to administering the questionnaires, the researcher obtained approval from the school's division superintendent and district supervisors to conduct the study. Likewise, a letter requesting the respondents' cooperation was sent. The researcher created a Google link and posted the school page and the group of respondents.

Instructions are clear on how to complete the questionnaire. Enough time was given to the respondents to enable them to concentrate on each item. After administering the instruments, the data were entered into the computer. The study's results served as the basis for policy interventions for elementary teachers.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The statistical treatment for this study involved applying analytic techniques to analyze the data collected through the research instrument. Each section of the instrument underwent statistical analyses tailored to address the study's research objectives and questions.

For Statement of Problem 1, frequency and percentage were used. These statistical tools were appropriate for describing the distribution and proportions of respondents across each category of ancillary services teachers provided. For Statement of Problem 2, the weighted mean and standard deviation were used. The weighted mean measured the central tendency, or average, of learners' academic performance, while the standard deviation measured the variability, or consistency, of their academic performance. For Statement of Problem 3, the weighted mean, standard deviation, and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) were applied. These statistical tools assessed whether there were significant differences in learners' performance across schools of different sizes (small, medium, and large) based on the ancillary services provided by teachers. To classify the level of impact, the following ranges were used: 4.20–5.00 (very high impact), 3.40–4.19 (high impact), 2.60–3.39 (moderate impact), 1.80–2.59 (low impact), and 1.00–1.79 (no impact).

Ethical Consideration

The researcher strictly observed ethical standards in conducting the study. Permission and informed consent were obtained from the relevant authorities and participants prior to data collection. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were assured of confidentiality, privacy, and anonymity. Moreover, all data gathered was used solely for academic purposes and stored securely. Honesty and integrity were maintained in the reporting and interpretation of the results, ensuring that no information was falsified or misrepresented. Also, proper acknowledgment of sources was observed to avoid plagiarism. Finally, the study ensured that no participant was harmed and that the findings would contribute positively to improving the distribution of teachers' ancillary services and enhancing learners' academic performance.

Results and Discussion

Status of Ancillary Services

This section discusses the status of teachers' ancillary services, including the identified ancillary services, the number of hours rendered, and the number of years assigned. For the distribution of ancillary services assigned to the teacher-respondents, the data reflect a uniform distribution across all identified ancillary roles:

1. Administrative and Operations Support - roles include ICT Coordinator, LIS/EBEIS Coordinator, SBM Coordinator, Property Custodian, Records In-charge, and Research Coordinator.
2. Student and Community Services - roles include Gulayan sa Paaralan Coordinator, SDRRM (Disaster Risk Reduction) Coordinator, WINS (Wash in Schools) Coordinator, SWM (Solid Waste Management) Coordinator, PESS (Physical Education and School Sports) Coordinator, and Health Coordinator.
3. Subject Area Coordinatorship - the list encompasses coordinators for all major learning areas: Reading, English, Science, ESP (Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao), MAPEH, Math, Filipino, Araling Panlipunan (AP), and MTB-MLE.

Figure 6. Percentage of Teachers Assigned to Ancillary Services

Each of the 22 listed specific ancillary services—along with an "Others" category—had a frequency of 537 respondents, representing 5.59% per category. This uniform frequency suggests a standardized assignment of these duties within the sample group or that the study design selected an equal number of coordinators for each designation. The frequency and percentage of teachers assigned to each of the 22 ancillary services in the school, with 30 teachers (5.59%) assigned to each service. Since teachers may hold more than one coordinator, the total percentage exceeds 100%. This indicates that several teachers perform multiple ancillary functions in addition to their teaching responsibilities.

The extensive breadth of non-teaching duties is currently shouldered by public school teachers. The list of ancillaries confirms the "jack-of-all-trades" phenomenon discussed by Uniforme and Obenza (2025), where teachers are not only instructional leaders (as subject coordinators) but also operational managers (as property custodians or LIS coordinators). The presence of distinct roles such as SDRRM and *Gulayan sa Paaralan* validates the observation that teachers absorb functions that, in larger organizations, would typically belong to specialized administrative or maintenance departments.

As illustrated in Figure 7, 100 % of the teachers indicated that they are assigned to at least one ancillary service, while none (0 %) reported having no ancillary duties. This clearly shows that all teachers have additional responsibilities beyond their teaching load (see Figure 7). The result implies that ancillary tasks are universally delegated among teachers regardless of their teaching assignment or school size, indicating that performing ancillary services has become a standard practice and an integral part of teachers' roles in schools.

Research on Filipino teachers confirms that ancillary duties, such as administrative work, student supervision, and event coordination, are prevalent and often extend beyond classroom instruction, thereby affecting workload and instructional time (Algar et al., 2025). Similarly, studies on teachers' ancillary functions show that public school teachers consistently take on multiple roles beyond their primary teaching duties, with implications for their professional responsibilities and self-efficacy (Pastoril & Oco, 2025).

Number of ancillary services	f	%
1 to 3	322	59.96%
4 to 5	185	34.45%
6 to 10	20	3.74%
More than 10	10	1.86%
Total	537	100%

Table 1. Number of Ancillary Services Assigned to Teachers

Table 1 shows that the majority of teachers (59.96%) reported handling 1 to 3 ancillary services, followed by 34.45% who were assigned 4 to 5. Only a small proportion of teachers (3.74%) managed 6 to 10 ancillary roles, while 1.86% handled more than 10 ancillary functions. These results indicate that most teachers in the schools are assigned to a manageable number of ancillary tasks, typically between one and three. However, a notable portion (about one-third) still carries four to five responsibilities, suggesting that some teachers experience moderate to heavy workload levels beyond their teaching duties. The small percentage of teachers with six or more assignments signifies that workload imbalance exists in some schools, possibly due to limited personnel or overlapping responsibilities. This finding supports the view of Bautista, Bernardo, and Ocampo (2020), who highlighted that teachers often juggle multiple non-teaching tasks, which can affect their instructional quality and work-life balance. Overall, the data imply that while ancillary assignments are generally distributed across teachers, administrators should still ensure equitable task distribution to avoid overloading certain staff members.

Number of hours rendered ancillary service	f	%
1	110	20.48%
2	207	38.55%
3	190	35.38%
More than 3	30	5.59%
Total	537	100%

Table 2. Number of Hours Rendered in Ancillary Services

Table 2 shows the distribution of teachers by the number of hours they provide for ancillary services. Out of the 537 respondents, the highest proportion (207 or 38.55 %) reported rendering 2 hours of ancillary service. This suggests that a significant number of teachers devote a moderate amount of time to additional school-related tasks aside from their teaching duties. Meanwhile, 190 teachers (35.38%) spend 3 hours on ancillary services, indicating that over one-third of respondents are significantly involved in non-teaching responsibilities. On the other hand, 110 teachers (20.48 %) spend only 1 hour, implying a smaller group with minimal ancillary involvement. Lastly, 30 teachers (5.59%) spend more than 3 hours on such activities, indicating that only a few are heavily engaged. Overall, the data revealed that most teachers provide 2–3 hours of ancillary service.

These findings align with prior research indicating that teachers frequently handle multiple non-teaching duties, such as administrative paperwork, student supervision, and coordination of school programs, which extend beyond their instructional hours (Villamayor et al., 2025). Such additional tasks can consume a substantial portion of teachers' time, potentially affecting their instructional preparation, classroom performance, and overall workload balance (Department of Education, IDinsight, & Policy Brief Team, 2025). Furthermore, studies have shown that increased engagement in ancillary duties is associated with work-related stress and reduced teaching effectiveness, particularly when teachers must manage both instructional and non-instructional responsibilities simultaneously (Gudelos and Mabitad, 2025). These findings underscore the significant role ancillary services play in teachers' professional workload and the importance of managing these responsibilities to maintain instructional quality.

Number of Years Assigned Ancillary Services	<i>f</i>	%
1	22	4.09%
2	53	9.87%
3	175	32.59%
More than 3	287	53.45%
Total	537	100%

Table 3. Number of Years Assigned in Ancillary Services

Table 3 presents the distribution of teachers according to the number of years they have been assigned to ancillary services. Among the 537 respondents, the majority (287, or 53.45%) have been assigned to ancillary duties for more than 3 years, suggesting that more than half of the teachers have extensive experience handling additional responsibilities beyond their primary teaching functions. Meanwhile, 175 teachers (32.59%) have been assigned to three-year roles, indicating that a considerable proportion of teachers have maintained ancillary roles for a sustained period. On the other hand, 53 teachers (9.87 %) have served for two years, and only 22 teachers (4.09 %) have been assigned to one-year assignments, indicating a relatively small group of relatively new participants in ancillary service assignments. Overall, the data imply that most teachers have long-term involvement in ancillary services. This reflects the common practice of repeatedly assigning the same teachers to non-instructional tasks over the years, which can enhance their familiarity and efficiency in these roles but may also increase workload and occupational fatigue.

These findings are consistent with previous studies showing that teachers are often assigned to ancillary and administrative functions because of their experience and perceived competence (Villamayor et al., 2025). Long-term assignment to such duties has been found to strengthen task proficiency; however, it also increases the risk of work overload and burnout, particularly when combined with full teaching loads (Pastoril & Oco, 2025; Department of Education, IDinsight, & Policy Brief Team, 2025). Similarly, research on teacher workload indicates that prolonged exposure to non-teaching responsibilities reduces time for instructional preparation and may negatively affect teaching performance and well-being (Torres et al., 2023). Thus, the sustained involvement of teachers in ancillary services, as shown in the present data, supports existing literature emphasizing the need for equitable task distribution and workload management in schools.

Academic Performance of Learners under Teachers with Ancillary Services

This section discusses the academic performance of learners under teachers with ancillary services.

No.	Small schools				Medium school				Large schools		
	Name of schools	Average of learners	Descriptor	No.	Name of schools	Average of learners	Descriptor	No.	Name of schools	Average of learners	Descriptor
1	Pambilán ES (8)	88	Very satisfactory	1	RT Camacho (17)	88	Very satisfactory	1	Alabat CES (45)	90	Outstanding

2	San Andres Bundok ES (3)	86	Very satisfactory	2	Rizal ES (12)	90	Outstanding	2	Atimonan CES (50)	92	Outstanding
3	Anahawan ES (8)	88	Very satisfactory	3	Municipal Sector ES (13)	90	Outstanding	3	Calauag East CES (34)	94	Outstanding
4	Mabini ES (5)	89	Very satisfactory	4	Gregorio Mendoza ES (13)	90	Outstanding	4	Guinayang an ES (40)	93	Outstanding
5	Rosario ES (7)	90	Outstanding	5	Progreso ES (12)	89	Very satisfactory	5	Gumaca West CES (40)	94	Outstanding
6	Talolong ES (8)	88	Very satisfactory	6	Don Mateo Lopez ES (12)	90	Outstanding	6	Lopez West ES Bldg. 1 (40)	94	Outstanding
7	Mainit Norte ES (8)	90	Outstanding	7	Perez West ES (25)	88	Very satisfactory	7	NONE	NONE	NONE
8	Tanauan ES (8)	90	Outstanding	8	Plaridel CES (25)	90	Outstanding	8	NONE	NONE	NONE
9	Cometa (6)	90	Outstanding	9	Gumubat ES (10)	89	Very satisfactory	9	Quezon ES (30)	90	Outstanding
10	Payapa ES (8)	89	Very satisfactory	10	Magsaysay ES (14)	90	Outstanding	10	Tagkawayan CES (45)	92	Outstanding
General average		88.80	Very satisfactory	General Average		89.40	Very satisfactory	General Average		92.38	Outstanding

Table 4. Academic Performance of Learners under Teachers with Ancillary Services

Table 4 presents the average grades and performance descriptions of learners from small, medium, and large schools. Small schools have an average grade range of 86 to 93, with most rated “very satisfactory” and a few rated “outstanding.” Their general average of 88.80 corresponds to a “very satisfactory” level, indicating that learners in small schools generally perform well and maintain consistent academic achievement. Medium schools have an average grade range of 88 to 90, with most rated as “very satisfactory” and several achieving “outstanding.” Their overall average of 89.40 also falls within the “very satisfactory” range, suggesting a stable learning environment conducive to academic success. Meanwhile, large schools show an average grade range from 90 to 94, all rated as “outstanding,” with a general average of 92.38. Learners from large schools consistently achieve higher academic results than those from smaller schools.

These findings show a progressive increase in average grades with school size, suggesting that school size and available institutional resources may positively influence learners’ academic performance. Recent studies indicate that larger schools tend to have better access to instructional resources, support personnel, and structured systems that enhance learner outcomes (Department of Education, IDinsight, & Policy Brief Team, 2025; Villamayor et al., 2025). Furthermore, institutional capacity in large schools may reduce the burden of ancillary services on teachers by distributing tasks more efficiently, allowing teachers to sustain “outstanding” instructional quality despite additional responsibilities (Pastoril & Oco, 2025).

In contrast, teachers in small schools are often required to perform multiple ancillary roles simultaneously, functioning as “jack-of-all-trades” (e.g., property custodian, canteen manager, and guidance counselor), which may divide their attention between teaching and non-teaching functions. This situation is supported by recent workload studies showing that excessive ancillary duties reduce instructional focus and contribute to role strain and fatigue, especially in schools with limited manpower (Department of Education, IDinsight, & Policy Brief Team, 2025; Torres et al., 2023).

Based on these results, school size appears to be a significant predictor of learners’ academic performance among teachers with ancillary services, with larger school environments fostering higher academic achievement. Contrary to the assumption that extra duties always weaken teaching effectiveness, recent findings by Salise et al. (2021) and the Bohol Schools Division Office (2023) revealed a positive relationship between ancillary functions and work performance. These studies suggest that teachers entrusted with ancillary roles often demonstrate higher self-efficacy, leadership capacity, and organizational skills, which translate into improved classroom management and instructional delivery. Thus, the effect of ancillary services on academic performance is influenced not only by workload but also by school context and support systems.

Impact of Ancillary Services on the Performance of Learners

This section discusses the impact of ancillary services on learners' performance.

No.	Statements	M	Verbal interpretation
1.	Ancillary tasks reduce the time I can focus on teaching and preparation.	3.10	Low impact
2.	My ancillary duties affect my classroom management and student engagement.	2.89	No impact
3.	Students' academic performance declines when teachers are overloaded with tasks.	2.75	Low impact
4.	Learners' academic progress improves when teachers are given fewer non-teaching duties	4.80	High impact
5.	Ancillary services offer opportunities to enhance school programs and improve learning outcomes.	3.23	Moderate impact
6.	My ancillary role helps strengthen students' holistic development.	2.87	Moderate impact
7.	Excessive ancillary work contributes to teacher burnout, which in turn affects teaching quality.	2.77	Moderate impact
8.	The balance between teaching and ancillary duties affects student learning performance.	5.00	Very high impact
9.	Ancillary roles improve coordination among teachers, indirectly benefiting learners.	3.15	Moderate impact
10.	Overall, ancillary services have a significant impact on learners' academic achievement.	3.39	Moderate impact
Overall weighted mean		3.40	High impact

Table 5. Impact on Learners' Academic Performance in Small Schools

Table 7 presents teachers' perceptions of the impact of ancillary services on learners' academic performance in small schools. The overall weighted mean of 3.40, interpreted as "high impact", suggests that teachers in small schools strongly agree that ancillary duties influence their teaching performance and learners' outcomes. The highest-rated statement ($M = 5.00$) indicates that teachers strongly agree that balancing teaching and ancillary duties significantly affects student learning. Likewise, the finding that learners' academic progress improves with fewer non-teaching duties ($M = 4.80$) underscores the importance of workload balance in enhancing educational outcomes. These results are consistent with recent studies showing that excessive administrative and ancillary tasks reduce instructional focus and negatively affect classroom effectiveness (Department of Education, IDinsight, & Policy Brief Team, 2025; Villamayor et al., 2025).

Conversely, the lowest-rated statements concern teacher overload ($M = 2.75$) and burnout ($M = 2.77$), suggesting that although these conditions exist, respondents perceive their severity as relatively low. This implies that teachers compensate for the burden of ancillary services by working longer hours and exerting greater effort, reflecting strong professional commitment and self-efficacy. Similar findings were reported by Pastoril and Oco (2025), who observed that teachers assigned to ancillary roles often demonstrate high levels of self-efficacy and adaptability, enabling them to sustain instructional performance despite additional responsibilities.

Overall, the results reveal that while ancillary services contribute to school coordination and program implementation, they also challenge teachers' ability to focus on core instructional tasks. Teachers in small schools perceive a high impact ($M = 3.40$) of ancillary duties on their work environment, yet they continue to produce high student grades ($GA = 88.80$). This implies that teachers absorb the administrative burden in ways that prevent immediate declines in learner achievement, though not without cost to workload balance. Teachers further affirmed ($M = 4.80$) that reducing non-teaching duties would improve learner progress, indicating that the current workload arrangement in small schools is not optimal for maximizing learner potential.

This perception aligns with DepEd Order No. 002, s. 2024, which mandates the immediate removal of administrative tasks from teachers to allow them to concentrate on their primary instructional function. The policy is grounded in empirical evidence showing that administrative overload distracts teachers from teaching and weakens instructional quality (Department of Education, 2024; Department of Education et al., 2025). Thus, the high-impact perception identified in this study is supported by recent research and national education policy, underscoring the need for a balanced distribution of teaching and non-teaching responsibilities in small schools.

No.	Statements	<i>M</i>	Verbal interpretation
1.	Ancillary tasks reduce the time I can focus on teaching and preparation.	2.16	Low impact
2.	My ancillary duties affect my classroom management and student engagement.	2.24	Low impact
3.	Students' academic performance declines when teachers are overloaded with tasks.	2.00	Low impact
4.	Learners' academic progress improves when teachers are given fewer non-teaching duties	4.16	High impact
5.	Ancillary services offer opportunities to enhance school programs and improve learning outcomes.	2.97	Moderate impact
6.	My ancillary role helps strengthen students' holistic development.	3.33	Moderate impact
7.	Excessive ancillary work contributes to teacher burnout, which in turn affects teaching quality.	2.69	Moderate impact
8.	The balance between teaching and ancillary duties affects student learning performance.	2.49	Low impact
9.	Ancillary roles improve coordination among teachers, indirectly benefiting learners.	2.88	Moderate impact
10.	Overall, ancillary services have a significant impact on learners' academic achievement.	2.69	Moderate impact
Overall weighted mean		2.76	Moderate impact

Table 6. Impact on Learners' Academic Performance in Medium Schools

Table 6 presents a computed weighted mean of 2.76, interpreted as “moderate impact”, indicating that teachers in medium schools moderately agree that ancillary duties affect their teaching performance and learners' academic achievement. The highest-rated statement ($M = 4.16$) shows that respondents strongly agree that learners' academic progress improves when teachers are assigned fewer non-teaching duties. This finding emphasizes that teachers believe that reduced ancillary workloads allow greater instructional focus, leading to better student outcomes. Similar results were reported by Villamayor et al. (2025), who found that minimizing non-instructional responsibilities enables teachers to allocate more time to lesson preparation and learner engagement, thereby improving academic performance.

Meanwhile, the lowest-rated statements ($M = 2.00-2.24$) indicate that teachers perceive ancillary workload and overload as having low impact on classroom management and student engagement. This suggests that teachers in medium schools may have developed effective coping strategies or that ancillary tasks are more evenly distributed among staff. This observation is consistent with findings by Pastoril and Oco (2025), who noted that teachers with manageable ancillary roles demonstrate adaptability and maintain classroom effectiveness despite additional duties.

Overall, the findings imply that although ancillary services still influence teaching effectiveness, their impact is less pronounced in medium schools than in small schools. Teachers recognize both the positive contributions of ancillary roles, such as improved coordination and holistic learner development, and the challenges they present. Recent workload studies indicate that institutional staffing levels and organizational structure play a crucial role in moderating the effects of ancillary duties (Department of Education, IDinsight, & Policy Brief Team, 2025).

The data further suggest that medium schools represent a structural “sweet spot.” Unlike small schools, where limited manpower creates severe workload imbalance, medium schools appear to have sufficient personnel to distribute tasks more equitably, stabilizing the effects of ancillary duties and keeping their impact on teaching time relatively low ($M = 2.16$). This supports recent evidence that schools with moderate staff size achieve better workload equilibrium and instructional efficiency (Torres et al., 2023).

In medium schools, teachers view ancillary services not only as a source of workload but also as opportunities for professional growth and holistic development ($M = 3.33$). This shift reflects the transition from role conflict to role enrichment, where additional responsibilities enhance professional skills rather than hinder performance. Studies on distributed leadership and teacher role expansion show that involvement in non-teaching functions can strengthen teachers' organizational competence, leadership skills, and instructional effectiveness (Salise et al., 2021; Villamayor et al.,

2025). Thus, when survival pressure is reduced, as in medium schools, ancillary duties are more likely to enhance teachers' professional capacity rather than detract from instructional quality.

No.	Statements	M	Verbal interpretation
1.	Ancillary tasks reduce the time I can focus on teaching and preparation.	1.47	No impact
2.	My ancillary duties affect my classroom management and student engagement.	1.47	No impact
3.	Students' academic performance declines when teachers are overloaded with tasks.	2.23	Low impact
4.	Learners' academic progress improves when teachers are given fewer non-teaching duties	2.93	Moderate impact
5.	Ancillary services offer opportunities to enhance school programs and improve learning outcomes.	3.79	High impact
6.	My ancillary role helps strengthen students' holistic development.	2.75	Moderate impact
7.	Excessive ancillary work contributes to teacher burnout, which in turn impacts the quality of teaching.	2.17	Low impact
8.	The balance between teaching and ancillary duties affects student learning performance.	1.73	No impact
9.	Ancillary roles improve coordination among teachers, indirectly benefiting learners.	2.96	Moderate impact
10.	Overall, ancillary services have a significant impact on learners' academic achievement.	2.07	Low impact
Overall weighted mean		2.36	Moderate impact

Table 7. Impact on Learners' Academic Performance in Large Schools

Table 7 presents the computed overall weighted mean of 2.36, interpreted as "moderate impact", indicating that teachers in large schools generally perceive that ancillary services have a minimal effect on learners' academic achievement. The highest-rated statement ($M = 3.79$) shows that teachers agree that ancillary services provide opportunities to improve school programs and enhance learning outcomes. This finding suggests that large schools' superior staffing, support systems, and administrative structures enable teachers to take on additional duties without significantly disrupting instruction.

Overall, the results indicate that in large schools, ancillary roles have a limited impact on teaching effectiveness and student achievement. This may be attributed to adequate staffing, systematic task delegation, and established administrative structures that reduce teachers' workload (Villamayor et al., 2025; Torres et al., 2023). In this context, ancillary services are not perceived as burdens but as enhancements. Meanwhile, the high-impact rating on Item 5 ($M = 3.79$) suggests that roles such as event coordinator or club adviser function as mechanisms of distributed leadership, contributing to well-coordinated programs that support the school's instructional goals (Salise et al., 2021).

This interpretation aligns with the observed "outstanding" academic performance ($GA = 92.38$) of learners in large schools, demonstrating that ancillary duties, when properly supported, can coexist with high student achievement. Teachers in large schools appear to leverage ancillary tasks as professional development opportunities, transitioning from role survival in small schools to role enrichment in larger institutions. Similarly, recent studies emphasize that well-staffed schools with clear role distribution and support systems enable teachers to manage non-teaching duties without compromising instructional quality (Pastoril & Oco, 2025; Department of Education, IDinsight, & Policy Brief Team, 2025).

Finally, while DepEd Order No. 002, s. 2024 aims to reduce administrative overload to improve teaching focus, the present findings suggest that such an intervention is most urgent in small schools, where limited capacity creates significant role conflict. In contrast, large schools have effectively balanced ancillary responsibilities, mitigating the need for immediate policy-driven adjustments (Department of Education, 2024). These findings highlight the importance of school context, staffing, and internal capacity in moderating the impact of ancillary duties on teaching effectiveness and learner outcomes.

School type	<i>M</i>	Verbal interpretation
Small Schools	3.40	High impact
Medium Schools	2.76	Moderate impact
Large Schools	2.36	Moderate impact
Grand mean	2.84	Moderate impact

Table 8. Summary of Overall Impact for Each Type of School

Table 8 shows a significant difference among the three groups—small, medium, and large schools—in their weighted mean perceptions of the impact of ancillary tasks. Teachers in small schools reported the highest perceived impact ($M = 3.40$), indicating that ancillary tasks strongly affect teaching performance and learners’ academic outcomes. In these schools, limited staffing and resources often require teachers to perform multiple ancillary roles simultaneously, creating role conflict and workload pressures that can interfere with instructional focus (Department of Education, IDinsight, & Policy Brief Team, 2025; Torres, Santos, & Dizon, 2023). Teachers’ high perceptions of impact in small schools align with studies that emphasize that excessive ancillary duties in resource-limited settings can constrain instructional time, reduce lesson preparation opportunities, and increase the risk of occupational stress (Pastoril & Oco, 2025).

Medium schools reported a moderate impact ($M = 2.76$), suggesting that while ancillary duties still influence teaching and learning, their effect is less pronounced compared to small schools. Medium-sized schools often have sufficient personnel to distribute ancillary tasks more effectively, reducing role conflict and allowing teachers to focus more on instructional activities (Villamayor et al., 2025). Research on medium-sized schools has shown that adequate staffing and task delegation can transform ancillary roles from burdensome obligations into opportunities for skill development and professional growth, reflecting the concept of role enrichment in role theory (Salise et al., 2021).

Large schools, on the other hand, exhibit the lowest perceived impact of ancillary duties ($M = 2.36$). In these settings, teachers typically operate within well-established administrative structures, benefit from role specialization, and have access to support personnel. These conditions allow teachers to perform ancillary functions without significant disruption to instructional quality, effectively transforming ancillary duties into enhancements rather than burdens (Villamayor et al., 2025; Department of Education, 2024). This finding corroborates evidence that distributed leadership and supportive school environments in larger institutions help teachers integrate non-teaching responsibilities while maintaining high student achievement (Salise et al., 2021).

Overall, the observed gradient in weighted means—from high impact in small schools, moderate in medium, to low in large schools—highlights the importance of school context, staffing capacity, and institutional support in moderating the effects of ancillary services on teaching effectiveness and learner outcomes. This trend underscores the need for policy interventions, such as DepEd Order No. 002, s. 2024, to prioritize workload alleviation in small schools while recognizing that medium and large schools may already have internal mechanisms to mitigate the impact of ancillary duties (Department of Education, 2024; Department of Education et al., 2025).

Source of variation	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i> -Computed	<i>F</i> -Critical (0.05)	Decision interpretation	Remarks
Between Groups	5.504	2	2.752	18.35	3.35	Reject H_0 Significant	High impact
With Groups	4.050	27	0.150				
Total	9.554	29					

Table 9. One-Way ANOVA on the Impact of Ancillary Tasks Among Small, Medium, and Large Schools

Table 9 shows that the computed F -value of 18.35 exceeds the critical F -value (0.05, 2, 27) = 3.35, indicating that the differences in teachers' mean responses across the three school groups—small, medium, and large—are statistically significant. This demonstrates that the perceived impact of ancillary tasks varies significantly by school size. Teachers in small schools ($M = 3.40$) rated ancillary tasks as having a high impact, suggesting that additional duties substantially affect instructional focus, classroom management, and student performance. Medium schools reported a moderate impact ($M = 2.76$), indicating that ancillary duties affect teaching performance and learner outcomes, though less severely than in small schools. Meanwhile, large schools perceived a low impact ($M = 2.36$), suggesting that larger staffing and support systems

enable better distribution or delegation of ancillary responsibilities (Department of Education, IDinsight, & Policy Brief Team, 2025; Villamayor et al., 2025).

The observed trend of higher perceived impact in small schools aligns with studies indicating that limited staffing and heavy non-teaching responsibilities create role conflict, workload stress, and diminished instructional focus (Pastoril & Oco, 2025; Torres, et al., 2023). Medium-sized schools, with moderate staffing levels, tend to experience role enrichment, in which ancillary tasks provide professional growth opportunities without substantially undermining teaching effectiveness (Salise et al., 2021). In large schools, the low perceived impact reflects adequate manpower, task specialization, and distributed leadership, which mitigate the effects of ancillary duties on both teaching and learners' academic outcomes (Villamayor et al., 2025).

The results confirm that school size is a key moderating factor in the relationship between ancillary service responsibilities and academic performance. This has implications for education policy, such as DepEd Order No. 002, s. 2024, which recommends reducing administrative burdens for teachers. Based on the present findings, such interventions are most critical in small schools, where ancillary tasks have the greatest impact, while medium and large schools may already possess internal mechanisms to balance teaching and non-teaching responsibilities effectively (Department of Education, 2024; Department of Education et al., 2025).

School size	Average ancillary service score	Average learners' grade	Computed impact score	Interpretation
Small	3.40	88.80	3.02	High impact
Medium	2.76	89.40	2.47	Moderate impact
Large	2.36	92.38	2.18	Moderate impact

Table 10. Impact Analysis by School

Interpreting the data through the lens of workload burden, Table 12 reveals a clear negative correlation between the level of ancillary services and learners' academic performance. Small schools, which reported the highest average ancillary service score ($M = 3.40$), representing the heaviest additional workload, also recorded the lowest average learners' grade (88.80). In contrast, large schools, with a lower ancillary service score ($M = 2.36$), achieved the highest average grade (92.38). This pattern suggests that high ancillary workload in smaller schools may divert teachers' attention from core instructional responsibilities, resulting in diminished academic outcomes (Department of Education, IDinsight, & Policy Brief Team, 2025; Torres et al., 2023).

The observed trend is consistent with recent empirical studies showing that excessive non-teaching duties in small schools can reduce instructional focus and increase teacher fatigue, which in turn lowers learner achievement (Pastoril & Oco, 2025; Villamayor et al., 2025). Ancillary duties in small schools contribute to extraneous cognitive load, where teachers' working memory and attention are divided between instructional and non-instructional tasks, limiting their capacity to maximize teaching effectiveness and learners' performance (Salise, et al., 2021). Conversely, medium and large schools with lower ancillary workloads benefit from better task distribution and role specialization, enabling teachers to allocate more cognitive resources to lesson planning, instructional delivery, and learner support (Villamayor et al., 2025).

In sum, the findings indicate that ancillary services in small schools, if not balanced with adequate support and staffing, may negatively affect teaching quality and learners' academic achievement. These results reinforce the necessity of workload management policies, such as DepEd Order No. 002, s. 2024, which seeks to reduce administrative burdens on teachers and optimize instructional outcomes (Department of Education, 2024; Department of Education et al., 2025).

Proposed Intervention Program / Policy Guidelines

The researcher emphasizes the need for a clear action plan or policy guideline on teachers' ancillary services, as such frameworks provide a structured approach to understanding how the distribution and management of non-teaching tasks affect both teachers' performance and learners' academic outcomes. In this study, the presence or absence of formal policy guidelines is a critical factor influencing the results. Studies indicate that structured guidelines for ancillary duties help minimize role conflict, enhance workload management, and sustain instructional quality (Villamayor et al., 2025; Pastoril & Oco, 2025).

The implementation of policy guidelines on teachers' ancillary services plays a crucial role in shaping the quality of instruction and, consequently, learners' academic performance. Ancillary services are defined as additional responsibilities assigned to teachers beyond their regular teaching load, including coordinating school programs, managing records, serving

on committees, and supervising co-curricular activities. Proper policy ensures the fair and equitable distribution of ancillary duties, maintains a balance between teaching and non-teaching responsibilities in accordance with DepEd standards, enhances teacher efficiency and morale, and institutionalizes a transparent and systematic approach to assignments (Salise, et al., 2021; Torres et al., 2023).

These policy guidelines should be applicable to all teaching and non-teaching personnel assigned to ancillary duties in small, medium, and large schools within the division. Teachers' ancillary services are essential to the effective operation of schools; however, unequal workload distribution can lead to burnout, reduced teaching efficiency, and lower learner performance (Department of Education, IDinsight, & Policy Brief Team, 2025). A clear policy framework establishes a systematic, fair, and transparent process for assigning ancillary tasks, ensuring equity, promoting efficiency, and enhancing accountability. Furthermore, the structured assignment of ancillary roles fosters role enrichment, allowing teachers to pursue professional development opportunities while maintaining a focus on instructional quality (Villamayor et al., 2025).

In conclusion, instituting clear policy guidelines for teachers' ancillary services is vital for optimizing teacher performance and improving learner outcomes. Policies should include criteria for workload distribution, rotational assignment of ancillary roles, and monitoring mechanisms to ensure compliance and fairness. By doing so, schools can balance administrative and instructional responsibilities, prevent burnout, and enhance the overall academic environment (Pastoril & Oco, 2025; Salise et al., 2021)

Conclusion and Implications

Summary

This study assessed the impact of teachers' ancillary services on learners' academic performance in small, medium, and large schools within the Fourth Congressional District of Quezon Province. The district comprises municipalities in the Tayabas Isthmus and Alabat Island, including Alabat, Atimonan, Calauag, Guinayangan, Gumaca, Lopez, Perez, Plaridel, Quezon, and Tagkawayan. The study covered 28 schools within small, medium, and large schools where only three elementary schools were selected in each municipality. The study employed a descriptive-quantitative design, using frequency, percentage, weighted mean, standard deviation, and one-way ANOVA to analyze data gathered from 537 teacher respondents.

Summary of Findings

1. Based on the data presented, analyzed, and interpreted, the following findings were obtained.
2. On the status of ancillary services of teachers in terms of identified teacher's ancillary services, 30 teachers (5.59%) are assigned to each of the 22 ancillary services. The majority of teachers (59.96%) reported handling 1 to 3 ancillary services, followed by 34.45% who were assigned 4 to 5. Only a small proportion of teachers (3.74%) managed 6 to 10 ancillary roles, while 1.86% handled more than 10 ancillary functions. On the number of hours rendered in ancillary services, the highest proportion (207 or 38.55%) reported rendering 2 hours of ancillary service. Meanwhile, 190 teachers (35.38%) spend 3 hours on ancillary services, indicating that over one-third of the respondents are significantly involved in non-teaching responsibilities. On the other hand, 110 teachers (20.48%) spend only 1 hour, implying a smaller group with minimal ancillary involvement. Lastly, 30 teachers (5.59%) spend more than 3 hours on such activities, indicating that only a few are heavily engaged. Lastly, regarding the number of years assigned to ancillary services, the majority (287, 53.45%) have been assigned to ancillary duties for more than three years. Meanwhile, 175 teachers (32.59%) have been assigned to three-year roles, indicating that a considerable proportion of teachers have maintained ancillary roles for a sustained period. On the other hand, 53 teachers (9.87%) have served for two years, and only 22 teachers (4.09%) have been assigned for one year.
3. The academic performance of learners under the teachers with ancillary services showed that the general average grade of learners is 88.80 in small schools, 89.40 in medium schools, and 92.38 in large schools.
4. The impact of the teachers' ancillary services showed a high impact on the learners' academic performance in small schools, as evidenced by the weighted mean of 3.40; moderate impact in medium schools, as evidenced by the weighted mean of 2.76; and low impact in large schools, as evidenced by the weighted mean of 2.36.
5. The researcher proposes policy guidelines on teachers' ancillary services to serve as the framework for understanding how the distribution and management of non-teaching tasks affect both teachers' performance and learners' academic outcomes. In the study, the presence or absence of clear policy guidelines is a critical factor influencing the research outcomes.

Conclusions

1. Based on the findings, the following conclusions have been drawn:
2. Teachers across all school sizes handle multiple ancillary assignments, leading to increased workload and divided attention between teaching and administrative tasks.
3. Ancillary responsibilities have a significant impact on learners' academic performance, particularly in small schools where teacher manpower is limited.
4. The degree of impact lessens as school size increases, owing to better task delegation and institutional support systems.
5. Effective time management, proper workload distribution, and administrative assistance are crucial in ensuring that ancillary functions do not compromise the quality of instruction and learner achievement.
6. The findings underscore the need for policy intervention from the Department of Education to regulate the number of ancillary roles assigned to teachers and to recognize these additional functions through workload credits or incentive

Recommendations

In light of the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. For School Administrators. It is essential to rationalize the assignment of ancillary services among teachers to prevent overload, establish clear guidelines that limit the number of ancillary posts each teacher can hold, and provide administrative support staff to manage clerical and documentation tasks efficiently.
2. For Teachers. It is important to practice efficient time management and prioritization, balance teaching and non-teaching duties, collaborate with peers through task-sharing and mentoring, and engage in professional development programs focused on workload management and stress reduction.
3. For the DepEd. It is recommended to review and reinforce existing policies on teacher workload, such as DepEd Memorandum No. 291, s. 2008, institutionalize service credits, honoraria, or reductions in teaching loads for teachers handling multiple ancillary roles, and deploy clerical aides or administrative assistants—particularly in small schools—to help lessen teachers' non-instructional burdens.
4. For Future Researchers. It is recommended to conduct similar studies using qualitative methods, such as interviews or focus groups, to gain a deeper understanding of teachers' experiences, extend the study to secondary schools or private institutions to compare the impact of ancillary services across different settings, and investigate other factors influencing academic performance, such as teacher motivation, school leadership, and resource availability, while employing additional statistical tools, including regression analysis and standard deviation, to effectively measure and discuss the impact of ancillary services across various school sizes.

Acknowledgements

The researcher wishes to recognize all the people who contributed to the successful accomplishment of this study:

To ALMIGHTY GOD, the author of all things and the source of all knowledge.

To the Marinduque State University administrators for bridging the needs of teachers and school administrators for continuing professional development.

To Quezonian Educational College, Inc. administrators, for non-stop leveling of better education in the Province of Quezon.

To Dr. Diosdado P. Zulueta, Chairperson, Dr. Venus A. Victoria, Dr. Rizalie M. Lim, and Professor Panchito M. Labay, members of Oral Examination Committee, for their valuable input, which led to the success of this study.

To Dr. Leodegario M. Jalos, Jr., Chair of the Extension Program for Quezon Province, for his unwavering support, technical aid, and ongoing advice to the researcher to ensure the success of this study.

To Dr. Rizalie M. Lim, Dean of Graduate Studies at Quezonian Educational College, Inc., for her consistent support and dedication to graduate studies.

To Engr. Nelson Rufino M. Montejo, for sharing his expertise as a statistician, guidance, and support in the statistical analysis of data.

To Ms. Liezel M. Manoy, for her assistance during times of difficulty in submitting research results.

To Dr. Rommel C. Baustista, School District Supervisors and Principals, for their gracious permission to conduct this study in the Fourth Congressional District of Quezon.

To Maria Fe P. Cuya and family for their unwavering understanding and support, encouragement, and for constantly pushing the researcher to continue and complete the study.

To the respondents who participated in this research making it possible.

To all of them, I owe a debt of gratitude. Thank you.

Funding

This research received no external funding from any public, commercial, or not-for-profit funding agency, and no organization provided financial support for the conduct of the study, authorship, or publication of this article.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

References

- Abizada, A. (2024). Effect of class size on student achievement at public schools. *Heliyon/Education.Research*.<https://tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/2331186X.2023.2280306>
- Abdullah, N. A., Shamsi, N. A., Jenatabadi, H. S., Ng, B. K., & Mentri, K. A. C. (2022). Factors affecting undergraduates' academic performance during COVID 19: Fear, stress and teacher parents' support. *Sustainability*, 14(13), 7694. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14137694>
- Adamu, A., & Adamu, A. (2022). Academic performance and its influencing factors among learners. *International Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 5(2), 45–52. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/365189742>
- Akinde, T. M., & Oyetakin, A. I. (2025). School factors and academic performance of students in private secondary schools in Ondo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Allied Sciences (IJAS)*, 16(6), 69–79. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16033228>
- Alcantara, J. R. (2024). Ancillary functions and teaching performance appraisal of teachers in Davao Occidental. *Global Scientific Journal*, 12(1), 112–125.
- Ali, S. S., Bansal, A., & Sharma, S. K. (2021). Interactive teaching methods and their impact on self-directed learning and ownership of learning among engineering students. *Education and Information Technologies*, 26(4), 4547–4565
- Algar, R. G. J., Basañes, M., De La Luna, A. T., Jr., Jentelizo, J. A. A., Salbibia, M. G. A., & Trecho, J. A. (2025). Teachers' ancillary services and instructional performance. *International Journal of Educational Management Studies*, 14(1), 33–49. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/378412901>
- Alj, Z., & Bouayad, A. (2024). Multidimensional determinants of academic performance: Insights from undergraduate students in Moroccan universities. *Journal of Technology and Science Education*, 14(2), 607–621. <https://doi.org/10.3926/jotse.2404>
- Anilkumar, P. (2020). Effective teaching strategies for classroom instruction. *International Journal of Education and Learning*, 9(1), 12–20. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341122330>
- Bautista, M., Bernardo, A., & Ocampo, D. (2020). Teacher workload and its impact on instructional effectiveness [Unpublished manuscript]. Referenced in Scimatic. <https://scimatic.or/journals/11/pdfs/6024pdf>
- Bisschoff, C., & Ayeni, A. A. W. (2025). Assessing the impact of staff reported perceptions of students' helping seeking and adjustment on academic performance of students: A case of selected tertiary institutions. *Frontiers in Education*, 10, Article 1670588. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2025.1670588>
- Blatchford, P., Bassett, P., Brown, P., & Martin, C. (2021). School size, class size, and academic performance: Longitudinal evidence from the UK. *British Educational Research Journal*, 47(5), 1012–1036. <https://doi.org/10.1002/berj.3732>
- Bohol Schools Division Office. (2023). Report on the relationship between ancillary functions and work performance. Bohol Schools Division Office. University of Bohol Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 9(1), 57–85.
- Bungabong, M. L. (2023). Teacher burnout: The lived experiences of teachers with ancillary tasks in a national high school in Leyte. *American Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation*, 2(4), 15–22.
- Cachero, M. E., Enrique, W. D., & Espinosa, K. P. M. (2026). Teachers' workload and support system in basic education: Implications for well-being and instructional effectiveness. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 53, 1–15. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/399482371>
- Camboja, J. L., Jr., & Osias, E. M. (2025). Teachers' job satisfaction and learners' academic performance. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 13(2), 56–69. <https://www.apjmr.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/APJMR-2025.13.2.06.pdf>
- Campoamor, R. D. (2023). Ancillary services and teaching efficiency of public elementary teachers in Bohol. *Journal of Philippine Education Studies*, 7(1), 101–117. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/370552944>

- Carroza Pacheco, A. M., León del Barco, B., & Bringas Molleda, C. (2025). Academic performance and resilience in secondary education students. *Journal of Intelligence*, 13(5), 56. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jintelligence13050056>
- Cinco, M. P., & Sim, M. J. C. (2025). A case study on the influence of class size and teachers' workload on teachers' motivation and student performance in an urban secondary school. *Pantao (The International Journal of the Humanities and Social Sciences)*, 4(3), 3958–3971. <http://doi.org/10.69651/PIJHSS0403366>
- Darling-Hammond, L., Hyler, M. E., & Gardner, M. (2022). Teacher stress, workload, and instructional quality: Implications for student learning. *Educational Leadership Review*, 23(2), 45–63. <https://www.edleadershipreview.com>
- Delos Santos, A., & Manalo, R. (2022). Comparative analysis of teacher workload and burnout across school sizes in CALABARZON. *Philippine Journal of Education Studies*, 9(2), 45–60.
- Department of Education. (2007). DepEd Order No. 51, s. 2007: Guidelines on ancillary services. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2007/12/20/do-51-s-2007-guidelines-on-the-implementation-of-ancillary-services/>
- Department of Education. (2008). DepEd Memorandum No. 291, s. 2008: Teacher workload policy. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2008/09/19/dm-291-s-2008-teacher-workload/>
- Department of Education. (2015). DepEd NCR Memorandum No. 105, s. 2015. <https://depedncr.com.ph/memo105s2015.pdf>
- Department of Education, IDinsight, & Policy Brief Team. (2025). Understanding teacher workload as a systemic issue: Findings from the IDinsight study on informing national staffing standards for non-teaching personnel (Policy brief). Government of the Philippines. https://edcom2.gov.ph/media/2025/03/EDCOM2_Policy-Brief_Ancillary-Workload.pdf
- Department of Education. (2018). Regional Memorandum No. 550, s. 2018. <https://region4a.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/RM-550-s-2018.pdf>
- Department of Education. (2020). DepEd Order No. 31, s. 2020: Guidelines on grading system. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2020/07/20/do-31-s-2020-guidelines-on-the-implementation-of-the-grading-system/>
- Department of Education. (2024). DepEd Order No. 05, s. 2024: Work hours and ancillary services. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2024/02/09/do-05-s-2024-work-hours-of-public-school-teachers/>
- EDCOM II. (2023). Teacher workload study in Philippine public schools. Second Congressional Commission on Education. <https://edcom2.gov.ph/reports/teacher-workload-study.pdf>
- Eryilmaz, N. (2025). Teacher job satisfaction: International evidence on the role of school working conditions. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 39(4), 789–805. <https://www.sciencedirect.com>
- Francisco, C. S., Tupaz, G. B., & Astilla, M. T. B. (2024). Teacher burnout: The lived experiences of teachers with ancillary tasks in a national high school in Leyte. *American Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation*.
- Frontiers in Psychology. (2025). Teacher support as a mediator between academic resilience and academic performance. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 16, Article 102345. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2025.102345>
- Gershenson, S., & Langbein, L. (2015). The effect of primary school size on academic achievement. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 37(1_suppl), 135S–155S.
- Gonzales, M. G., Guimary, F. M., & Gabunilas, L. M. (2022). Teacher's workload and well being and their implication to learners' academic performance. *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education*, 14(3)
- Gudelos, J.T., & Mabitad, B.D. (2025) Work-Related Stress, Workloads, and Performance: A Case of Senior High School Teachers. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 9(1), 147-1471. <https://doi.org/10.47772/IJRISS.2025.9010121>.
- Jerrim, J., & Sims, S. (2021). When is high workload bad for teacher wellbeing? Accounting for the non-linear contribution of specific teaching tasks. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 105, 103395. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2021.103395>
- Kasperczuk, A., Cwiakala, M., Gorka, E., Reczajski, P., Frasnkiwicz, M., Darcinska-Glebocka, A., Piwnik, J., & Gardocki, G. (2025) The role of work-life balance in effective business management. *Scientific Papers of Silesian University of Technology. Organization and Management Series*, 215, 149-158.
- Kraft, M. A., Marinell, W. H., & Yee, D. S. (2020). School organizational contexts, teacher turnover, and student achievement. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 42(2), 283–308. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0162373720906828>
- Llego, M. A. (2021). DepEd teachers' workload policy study: Heavy workload and its impact on teaching responsibilities. *TeacherPH*. Retrieved from <https://www.teacherph.com/deped-teachers-workload-policy-study>
- Marín, Y. R., Quiñones Huatangari, L., Alva Tuesta, J. N., Cruz Caro, O., Maicelo Guevara, J. L., Sánchez Bardales, E., & Chávez Santos, R. (2025). Analysis of factors affecting the academic performance of university students using machine learning. *Scientific Reports*, 15(1), 44027. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-28870-1>
- Medina-Garrido, J.A., Biedma-Ferrer, J.M., & Ramos-Rodriuez, A.R. (2023). Relationship between work-family balance, employee well-being and job performance (Working Paper No. 2401.13683).arXiv. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2401.13683>.
- Ojedokun, O. A. (2022). School environment and students' academic performance. *African Journal of Educational Studies*, 16(3), 144–158. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/360284129>

- Open Access. (n.d.). Factors affecting students' academic performance. *Open Access Journal of Education*, 4(1), 1–15. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341104622>
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2023). *Education at a Glance 2023:OECD Indicators*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/e13b3f63-en>
- Pamunag, J. R., & Mosquera, L. R. (2025). Teacher workload and teaching performance. *Journal of Educational Leadership and Policy*, 11(2), 77–90. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/379001235>
- Pastoril, J. M., & Oco, E. L. (2025). Teachers' ancillary functions and self-efficacy. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning*, 18(1), 21–35. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/378215476>
- Pepito, J., Pepito, V., & Suson, R. (2024). Impact of multitasking on teachers' performance in public elementary schools. *International Journal of Education and Practice*, 12(1), 38–53. <https://doi.org/10.18488/61.v12i1.3587>
- Pierce, T., Smith, R., & Kline, J. (2023). Teacher support and students' academic performance in low- and high-stakes assessments. *Educational Psychology Review*, 35(4), 899–917. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10648-023-09712-3>
- PT Arsakha Cipta Nusantara (2025) The effect of teamwork and workload on employee performance through job satisfaction in employees. *International Journal of Asian Business and Management*, 4(4). <https://doi.org/10.55927/ijabm.v4i4.487>
- Salise, M. J., Dela Cruz, R. T., & Mendoza, L. P. (2021). Ancillary functions and teachers' work performance. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 35(4), 812–826.
- Salise, S. D., Sales, E. L., & Belgira, K. A. (2021). Classroom performance and ancillary functions among secondary school teachers in the Third District of Bohol. *University of Bohol Multidisciplinary Research Journal*.
- Santos, A. B., & Dela Cruz, C. D. (2021). Teachers' workload, burnout, and instructional focus: Balancing primary responsibilities with ancillary duties [Unpublished/institutional report]. Findings reported in National Institute of Joint School Education article.
- Skinner, B. F. (1974). *About behaviorism*. Knopf. ISBN 0394495400
- Suleiman, I. B., Okunade, O. A., & Dada, E. G. (2024). Key factors influencing students' academic performance. *Journal of Electrical Systems and Information Technology*, 11(1), Article 41. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43067-024-00166-w>.
- Slideshare. (n.d.). DepEd teacher's workload policy study. <https://www.slideshare.net/slideshow/dep-ed-teacher-s-workload-policy-study-pptx/271786409>
- SplashLearn. (n.d.). Effective teaching strategies for the classroom. <https://www.splashlearn.com/blog/teaching-strategies/>
- Thorndike, E. (1999) *Education Psychology*. New York: Routledge. ISBN 0415210119
- Tolentino, M. R. (2021). Teachers' ancillary roles in Philippine public schools. *Philippine Journal of Education*, 100(3), 45–60. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/349875214>
- Torres, J. M., Santos, R. L., & Dizon, P. A. (2023). Teachers' workload, stress, and instructional effectiveness in public schools. *Asia Pacific Journal of Educational Management*, 6(2), 55–68.
- Torres, C., & Maldonado, J. (2023). Organizational management practices and school performance in Latin America. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 93, 102651. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2023.102651>
- Tutor, J. P., & Elbanbuena, M. S. (2024). Ancillary services and teachers' performance levels. *International Journal of Educational Research and Innovation*, 9(1), 65–79. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/374889211>
- Uniforme, G., & Obenza, B. (2025). Resilience under pressure: A case study of head teachers' ancillary functions in the Philippine public education system. *Asia Pacific Journal of Educational Technologies, Psychology, and Social Sciences*, 1(2), 36–57. <https://doi.org/10.70847/632673>
- Valderrama, N. G. A. (2025). Multi-tasking role and functions of classroom advisers in public secondary schools, Division of Laguna. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*. <https://rsisinternational.org/journals/ijriss/articles/multi-tasking-role-and-functions-of-classroom-advisers-in-public-secondary-schools-division-of-laguna/>
- Villamayor, R., Dugan, J., & Ricafort, F. (2025). Balancing act: Exploring the impact of ancillary duties on Filipino teachers' professional lives. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 9(3), 846–855. <https://rsisinternational.org/journals/ijriss/articles/balancing-act-exploring-the-impact-of-ancillary-duties-on-philipino-teachers-professional-lives/>
- Weiner, B. (2008). *The social psychology of school achievement: Individual differences and cultural variations*. Routledge. ISBN 9780415998505
- Work Related Stress, Workloads, and Performance: A Case of Senior High School Teachers. (2025). *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*. <https://rsisinternational.org/journals/ijriss/articles/work-related-stress-workloads-and-performance-a-case-of-senior-high-school-teachers/>
- Wijaya, T. T., Yu, B., Xu, F., Yuan, Z., & Mailizar, M. (2023). Analysis of Factors Affecting Academic Performance of Mathematics Education Doctoral Students: A Structural Equation Modeling Approach. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(5), 4518. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20054518>

Zhang, L., & Chen, H. (2024). Teacher workload and student academic outcomes: Evidence from public schools in China. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 25, 101–115. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12564-024-09987-4>

Appendices

Appendix A. Questionnaire

The questionnaire developed for this study is made openly accessible as a supplementary research instrument. It is deposited in a public scholarly repository associated with this article. In addition, a version-controlled copy of the working sheet, together with accompanying documentation and update history, is hosted in a public GitHub repository.